

SOURCES OF FINANCIAL AND CREDIT SUPPORT AND FACTORS HINDERING THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES

Aziza Mahomadrizoevna Karimova

**Senior Lecturer, PhD, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service,
Uzbekistan**

Annotation. This article examines the importance and role of the tourism industry in the development of the country's economy, examines the factors hindering its development, as well as problems related to the sources of financing of this activity. Currently, tourism has become one of the most promising areas of activity, however, according to research, there are now many problems faced by the subjects. The article analyzes the activities and provides proposals, the implementation of which would contribute to solving existing problems related to the financial aspects of the activities.

Keywords: tourism, bank, lending, financing, crediting, subject of tourist activity, own funds, cash, borrowed funds, investments, accumulation of funds

Introduction. Currently, tourism is one of the fastest growing sectors of the economy of many developed and developing countries of the world. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO): "Today, 10.9% of the world's gross domestic product (GDP), 7% of total exports and 30% of exports of services, 9% of jobs are accounted for by tourism. According to forecasts, by 2028, the volume of tourism services on a global scale will reach 12.5 trillion US dollars, its share in world GDP will be 11.7%.¹" The importance of tourism enterprises for the economy is actualized by the study of the current state, credit support of tourism entities. The banking system of developing countries is not able to fully meet the needs of entrepreneurs who are already operating in the tourism industry or intend to open their own tourism business.

¹UNWTO. Tourism Highlights: 2019 Edition, p.3/<http://www.unwto.org>; <http://www.unwto.org>; <http://www.interfax.ru/business/>

This determines the importance of improving the current lending procedure and developing a different mechanism of bank lending for tourism enterprises.

In world practice, a significant amount of scientific research is devoted to the study of credit support for enterprises. The methodological basis was studied and the mechanism of crediting enterprises was analyzed, as well as scientific developments were made in the field of improving credit support for enterprises. As a result of these studies, noteworthy scientific and theoretical concepts and experience of lending to enterprises in international lending practice have been collected. Meanwhile, the tourism enterprises we are investigating today are at different levels of development, and the results achieved at the international level of improving the mechanism of their credit support are not sufficiently disclosed. The application of world experience and knowledge in individual countries requires more in-depth scientific research.

Tourism is one of the priorities for the development of the economy and culture of the republic Uzbekistan is a bright and inspired country of the East. The presence of ancient sights in the Republic, mosques, mausoleums, madrassas, as well as many untouched corners of nature, medical centers, many resources allow the development of many types of tourism.

World-famous historical monuments, modern cities, unique nature of Uzbekistan, unique national cuisine, as well as unsurpassed hospitality of our people attract travel lovers. Thanks to this, a breakthrough is possible in the country in obtaining foreign exchange earnings from tourism activities and replenishing the country's budgets. In other words, the tourism industry produces a tourist product that is in demand both on the foreign and domestic market.

The main task of the tourism industry is to create a high-quality and in-demand tourist product.

The activity of the tourism sector is formed at the level of organizations of various processes: that is, the production of goods, the provision of high-quality services, skills, qualifications and professionalism of personnel, sufficiency of financing, preferential taxation, etc. all this is an integral part of the activity, without which development is impossible.

The process of improving tourism activities is not possible without the involvement of tourist resources such as cultural attractions of the city, the landscape of the city, entertainment facilities and recreation areas. Due to the absence of a tax on tourist resources, they are relatively cheap, which contributes to the high profitability of the tourist business.

It follows from this that the Republic of Uzbekistan creates favorable conditions for attracting investments in the tourism sector, is based on a targeted policy within the framework of the action strategies program.

Theoretical background. Issues related to the financial and socio-economic aspects of tourism play an important role in the development of the country's economy. The system of financing as a sphere of management is considered and analyzed in the works of many domestic and foreign economists, including: I.Balabanov, A.T.Bykov, A.Y.Alexandrova, G.A.Karpov, E.V. Egorov, N.I.Filatov, I.Schumpeter, K.Marx, I.Fischer, etc.

However, it should be noted that scientists have not yet sufficiently investigated all the financial aspects of the development and functioning of representatives of the tourism sector, thus, there is a need for further development of the theory and practice of financial support for the activities of the tourism sector.

Main part. Creating favorable conditions for financial activity is an important element of tourism management. Not only tourist business organizations (travel agencies, travel agencies, hotels, manufacturing, consulting) need financing, consumer

demand for lending, for example, vacations, also needs financial support. Therefore, the financing of this sphere plays an important role in the country's economy.

To begin with, let's consider the concept and essence of financing itself, as well as its sources. Financing is understood as providing the necessary financial resources for the entire economy of the country, regions, enterprises, entrepreneurs, citizens, as well as various economic programs and types of economic activity.²

According to V.G.Medynsky, the financing system should be based on the following principles:

1) the target orientation of financing is its alignment with the task of rapid and effective implementation of modern scientific and technical developments;

2) validity and legal protection of funding sources;

3) multiple sources of financing;

4) the breadth and complexity of financing, i.e. the possibility of maximum coverage of a wide range of technical and technological innovations and directions of their use;

5) adaptability and flexibility of the financing system and its individual elements in order to take into account dynamically changing market conditions in order to maintain maximum efficiency.³

² Raizberg B.A., Lozovsky L.Sh., Starodubtseva E.B. Modern Economic Dictionary.-2nd ed.,ispr M.: INFRA-M.479 s.. 1999

³ Medynsky, V.G. Innovation management: Textbook / V.G. Medynsky. - M.: INFRA- M, 2012. - 295 p.

Own funds are understood as the use of own funds aimed at self-financing. Here, the funds of the founders can also act as a source, if several founders are registered in the authorized fund. The founders' funds are the company's own capital and if the business does not take place, the founders who invest money in turnover lose them.

The next type of financing is public. It is carried out on an irrevocable basis at the expense of budgetary, as well as extra-budgetary funds. As part of the implementation of state support for the activities of the tourism sector by the state, this type of financing is purposefully carried out.

In cases where there is a lack of own funds and there is no state support, the organization may resort to the use of borrowed funds, i.e. credit resources of the bank. The bank's credit resources or lending are understood as a form of financial security, in which expenses are covered by the lender's loans provided within the framework of the existing lending principles (i.e. urgency, repayment, security and payment).

Having dealt with the concept and essence of the financing itself and its source, we will consider below the various types of enterprises implementing tourism activities:

- hostels, hotels, rest houses, sanatoriums, other places where tourists stay;
- health resorts;

- restaurants, cafes, bars, snack bars, other places of public catering;
- transport, communication services, internet;
- zoos, sports grounds, amusement parks, other objects of the entertainment industry;
- rental and rental of vehicles;
- financial and organizational services.

As well as other tourist and related services, which should include:

- insurance services;
- enterprises of the banking sector;
- information, etc.

As stated above, the tourism industry is a combination of various subjects of tourist activity, which makes it possible to create additional new jobs, additional funds to the country's budget and ensure employment of the country's population. But, to date, practice and analysis shows the existence of a number of problems, the existence of which are obstacles to the development of this sphere.

The absence of a fully functioning mechanism of the tourism industry now reduces to the fact that Uzbekistan is losing large financial resources that would have entered the country's budget with an increase in the tourist flow. We know that a well-founded system of financing the tourism sector will create conditions for the accumulation of financial resources, as well as the possibility of their concentration on key areas of innovation processes.

Creating a fully functioning activity is often impossible without the active participation and financial assistance of the state. However, if we consider each element separately, it turns out that its creation is possible with private investments of companies and even individual investors.

When it comes to sources of financing and criteria of optimal economic category, the basis for the formation of the source of optimal financing should be sought secured prestigious relationships expressed by internal relations and sources of financing. Below we will consider the sources of financing investments in the tourism industry. From this scheme, we conclude that in practice, when financing the tourism sector, all types of financing can be used simultaneously.

Sources of tourism financing

1. funds of subjects of tourist activity
2. monetary contributions of legal entities and individuals;
3. borrowed funds (bond and other loans, bank and other loans);
4. foreign investments;
5. other sources, i.e. financing from various structures.

In addition to the sources of tourism financing listed above, in practice, all types of financing can be applied simultaneously. The main thing is to choose between them such a structure in which the goals and objectives of the tourism business will be achieved.

Today, the demand for lending is growing every day. Despite such a rapid development of the lending system, there are many problems in the system that most of those receiving a loan face.

The results of the analysis on the issuance of loans served as the basis for the systematic construction of an additional source of financing for the activities of the tourism sector.

Financing from commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the form of loans can be equated to the price of commercial and consumer loans, the interest rate of which is very high. For example, AICB "IPAK Yuli" issues a consumer loan secured by gold products and jewelry in the amount of 20 million rubles.sum with an interest

rate in cash of 31.9%, in non-cash of 29.9%, to the bank card Uzcard. For a period of 12 months. After calculating the percentage for the loan received, the analysis shows that the client pays an additional 6 380 million soums for using the loan. That is, the loan received costs him 26,380 million soums, which indicates that the loan received is very expensive. The same situation can be seen in Uzpromstroybank in which the loan is transferred to the account of a travel agency with a 28% rate for a period of 12 months in the amount of up to 100 MCI. (MRZP - 223,000 soums).⁴

Currently, the state pays great attention to the tourism sector, in January of this year, regulations important for the tourism sector were adopted: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5611 "On additional measures to accelerate the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" as well as Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4095 "On measures to accelerate the development of the tourism industry". These regulations define the main strategic directions for the development of the tourism sector. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5611 approved the Concept of development of the tourism sector in the period up to 2025 with the annual adoption of a plan of specific measures to implement the Concept.

The conducted research shows that despite the adoption of a number of regulations, as practice shows, there are a number of problems in the country today that are an obstacle to the development of the tourism sector. Such as:

- low efficiency of using the financial potential of the territory and state property;
- a high share of the shadow economy and the opacity of financial flows from market-developed countries;

⁴ <https://uzpsb.uz/uz/>

- the absence and non-professional provision of high-quality tourist services in hotels, transport services, services at catering facilities, etc.;
- the small number of countries with a simplified visa regime;
- lack of hotel complexes, as well as hotels with international class of service;
- underdeveloped infrastructure;
- underdevelopment and poor condition of networks of sanitary and hygienic nodes;
- low level and quality of the service sector;
- underdevelopment and poor service of operators, as well as the lack of a mobile network and Internet outside the city;
- the absence of a marketing company engaged in the study of this field of tourism;
- lack of well-established interaction between the state and private business;
- lack of development (improvement) of modern hospitality infrastructure with the involvement of international networks;
- lack of development of state regulation and support for the activities of organizations in the field of tourism;
- the lack of an industry management system that meets modern requirements in this area;
- not sufficiently formed material and technical base;
- shortage of professionally qualified personnel in the field of tourism.

There are also a number of factors that hinder the development of innovative activities in this area, which we will consider below in the form of a diagram: (Fig.1)

Fig.1. Factors hindering the development of innovative activities in the tourism sector⁵

The solution of these problems on the basis of the development of state regulation and support for the activities of the tourism sector will allow the most effective use of the existing tourism potential of the country.

⁵ developed by the author

Conclusion. Based on the results of the study, we offer the following suggestions and recommendations aimed at increasing the sources of financing for tourism activities and the development of this industry:

1. adoption of a regulatory legal act, ensuring the financing of investment needs and the establishment of a taxation system for all subjects of the tourism sector (provision of services, handicrafts, consumer demand, etc.);

2. establish additional benefits for foreign investors who raise their funds in this industry;

3. increase the share of state budget funds in the formation of monetary resources of tourist entities;

4. to reduce the interest rate on loans issued for the purchase of transport for travel agencies and travel agencies, the purchase of tour vouchers, the purchase of vouchers for treatment in sanatoriums, resorts, etc.;

5. notifications in the media about the possibility of creating and operating outside the budget Fund to support the tourism sector;

6. develop indicators of economic and social efficiency of attracted investments in the tourism sector.

And in conclusion, we can say that enterprises engaged in tourism activities are the most important part of the tourism sector. Consequently, a well-developed system of financing the tourism sector, on the one hand, will lead to additional funds in the country's budget revenues, and on the other hand, it will create additional jobs and provide employment for the population.

References

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "ON TOURISM" No. 830-I 20.08.1999
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "ON TOURISM" No. ZRU-549 on July 18, 2019
3. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banks and banking activities" N ZRU-580 dated 05.11.2019.
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5611 "On additional measures to accelerate the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated 5.01. 2019
5. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4095 "On measures for accelerated development of the tourism industry" dated 05.01.2019
6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5611 "Concept of development of the tourism sector in the period up to 2025"
7. Raizberg B.A., Lozovsky L.SH., Starodubtseva E.B. Modern Economic dictionary. -2nd ed., ispr M.: INFRA-M. 479 s. 1999.
8. Medynsky, V. G. Innovation management: Textbook / G. V. Medynsky. - M.: INFRA - M, 2012. - 295 p. Karimova A. M. Development of tourism business with the help of bank lending in Uzbekistan //SCIENCE, EDUCATION, INNOVATIONS: current issues and modern aspects. - 2021. - pp. 106-108.
9. Mahommadrezaevna K. A. Sources of financing and factors hindering the development of innovative activities of the sphere of tourism //Indonesian Journal of Innovation Studies. - 2020. - Vol. 9.
10. Karimova A.M. The need to improve credit support for innovative development of tourism enterprises //Journal Innovations in Economics. - 2021. - Vol. 4. - No. 1.
11. Jaxongir Z., Baxodir K., Aziza K. Financial and Credit Support of the State Tourism Entrepreneurs as a Result Measures Taken to Prevent the Consequences Coronavirus Pandemics in the Reforming New Uzbekistan in the Case of COVID 19 //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. - 2021. - pp. 6323- 6336-6323-6336.
12. Karimova A.M. (2020). Financial Support to Tourism Activities. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 29(7), 2010 - 2014. Retrieved from <http://serisc.org/journals/index.php/IJAST/article/view/17363>
13. <https://uzpsb.uz/uz/>
14. https://studref.com/480191/turizm/istochniki_finansirovaniya_turizma.